

UT Cafeteria Survey - Report Out

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of the UT Cafeteria Survey conducted by the PhD and EngD Network of the University of Twente (PE-NUT) to better understand experiences with day-to-day cafeteria services at the University of Twente. The survey collected responses from members of the university community, including students, PhD candidates, and staff, and focuses on key aspects such as price, food quality, menu variety, dietary accommodation, and perceived value. The results show a clear and consistent pattern of dissatisfaction with the current cafeteria offerings. The most prominent concern among respondents is price: many feel that the cost of meals is disproportionately high relative to both the quality and portion size of the food provided. This perception is reinforced when comparing cafeteria offerings to on-campus commercial alternatives, which are widely seen as providing better value for money. Concerns regarding menu variety and dietary inclusion were also frequently raised. While some respondents find the existing selection adequate, many report that the menu rotates too infrequently and does not sufficiently accommodate diverse dietary needs. Additionally, respondents overwhelmingly expressed that they do not feel they have any meaningful influence on menu decisions or the ability to provide feedback that leads to visible improvement. As a result of these issues, overall satisfaction with cafeteria services is low. These findings suggest that the challenges are structural rather than individual preference-based. This report aims to support constructive dialogue between the university, service providers, and the campus community, with the goal of developing a more inclusive, affordable, and responsive cafeteria system.

1 Introduction

To better understand perceptions of the current cafeteria offering at UT , we conduct a survey focusing on daily cafeteria services on campus. The purpose of the survey is to gather feedback regarding key dimensions that shape users' cafeteria experience, including price, quality, variety, and availability of food

and beverages. The responses will support evidence-based representation of the community’s interests in discussions with the university and food service providers. The scope of the survey is limited to the university-run cafeteria facilities used for day-to-day meals. It explicitly excludes event catering services and independently operated commercial outlets on campus such as SPAR, Subway, Starbucks, Frosty’s Poké Bowl, and rotating food trucks.

2 Methodology

This study uses survey-based data to assess experiences and perceptions of day-to-day cafeteria services at the University of Twente. The survey was conducted online using *Microsoft Forms* between 05.09.2025 and 31.10.2025. Access to the survey required a valid UT Microsoft account, ensuring that only members of the university community could participate while maintaining full anonymity of responses. The survey was distributed through multiple communication channels to reach a broad and diverse section of campus users, including PE-NUT WhatsApp community groups, the university internal email system, the PE-NUT newsletter, digital information screens on campus, and printed flyers distributed in university buildings. The questionnaire¹ consisted of both structured and open-ended items. Structured questions included:

- Multiple-choice items regarding user background (e.g., role at the university, frequency of cafeteria visits, dietary restrictions),
- Five-point Likert-scale items evaluating satisfaction with:
 - Food quality and taste,
 - Pricing and value for money,
 - Menu variety and accommodation of dietary needs,
 - Transparency of food labeling,
 - Perceived influence and feedback channels,
 - Overall experience and perceived fairness across user groups.
- A ranking task where respondents ordered the importance of factors such as location, price, food quality, food variety, speed of service, and seating availability.

Additionally, two open-ended questions invited respondents to provide elaborated feedback on desired improvements and overall impressions of the cafeteria system. While the survey provides valuable insights, its voluntary and convenience-based distribution limits the statistical generalizability of the results. However, the number and diversity of respondents and the richness of feedback make the dataset a basis for informing discussions on improving campus cafeteria services.

¹View Appendix A for the full questionnaire

Figure 1: Role distribution of respondents.

Figure 2: Frequency of using cafeteria offering.

3 Results

The survey sample includes 251 students, PhD/EngD candidates, scientific staff, and support staff across the University of Twente (see Figure 1). Most respondents report eating at campus cafeterias on a recurring basis (e.g., several times per week or per month), providing a relevant and experience-based perspective on the cafeteria offerings (see Figure 2).

The most pronounced result across the survey is dissatisfaction with pricing (see Figure 3) which also is perceived as the most important factor (see Figure 4). Out of the 251 respondents, about 95% disagree or strongly disagree that cafeteria food is reasonably priced for the quality offered. This perception is reinforced when respondents compare the cafeterias to commercial vendors also located on campus, where 93% disagree or strongly disagree that the cafeteria offers good value for money compared to alternatives. Responses regarding food quality and taste show more variation, but the overall trend leans toward dissatisfaction (about 60% disagree or strongly disagree). Respondents also expressed that they do not feel they have meaningful influence on menu decisions or cafeteria policies (90% disagree or strongly disagree). Desire for more opportunities to share feedback was consistently high (about 75% agree or strongly agree). About 90% of respondents agree or strongly agree to liking multiple cafeteria vendors on campus.

Overall ratings average to 4.2 out of 10 (see Figure 5). The Net Promoter Score of -91, calculated by Microsoft Forms, indicates that most respondents are not likely to recommend the cafeteria offering to a friend (see Figure 6).

Figure 3: Degrees of agreement of respondents to statements regarding the cafeteria offering.

Figure 4: Rank ordering of factors by importance for deciding where to eat on campus.

Figure 5: Overall rating of cafeterias on campus from 1-10 with 10 being the highest score.

Figure 6: Net Promoter Score.

4 Conclusion

The results of the survey indicate a consistent and systematic dissatisfaction with the current cafeteria offering at the University of Twente. Across respondents, three key themes emerged that collectively highlight issues in the present cafeteria offering. Firstly, prices are widely perceived as too high relative to the quality of the food provided. This concern is reinforced by respondents' assessments that the cafeterias do not offer good value for money when compared to on-campus commercial alternatives such as SPAR, Subway, or Frosty's Poké Bowl. Secondly, while opinions on menu variety are more mixed, a substantial proportion of respondents indicate that the existing menu rotation and diversity are insufficient to prevent repetition and monotony over time. This concern might disproportionately affect regular cafeteria users. Thirdly, respondents express that they do not feel they have any meaningful influence on menu decisions. The perceived absence of communication and feedback channels might contribute to frustration and disengagement. Consequently, overall satisfaction with the cafeteria offering is low. Taken together, these findings suggest that the current issues are structural rather than individual preference mismatches. Addressing them will likely require coordinated changes to pricing structures, offering, and avenues for community involvement in decision-making processes.

The findings presented in this report are based on responses to a voluntary survey. As participation was self-selected, the results may disproportionately reflect the views of individuals who have stronger opinions about the cafeteria services. For this reason, the data should be interpreted as indicative of user experiences rather than as a statistically representative sample of the entire university population. Additionally, while the survey captures recurring patterns in satisfaction and perceived value, it does not directly measure operational constraints such as supplier contracts, cost structures, or logistical considerations that may influence cafeteria pricing and menu decisions. The perspectives reported here therefore reflect user experience and perception, rather than a comprehensive operational evaluation. Despite these limitations, the consistency and volume of responses provide evidence for the patterns identified.

Declaration of Interest

This report was prepared by the PhD and EngD Network of the University of Twente (PE-NUT) in its role as an elected representative body for doctoral and EngD candidates at the University of Twente. PE-NUT receives standard institutional funding from the University of Twente to support its representative and community activities; however, the university did not influence the design of the survey, the data collection, the analysis, or the conclusions presented in this report. PE-NUT does not hold any operational, financial, or contractual interests in cafeteria services or food service vendors. No conflicts of interest are declared.

Data Availability

An anonymized version of the dataset is publicly available at

A Survey Questionnaire

The following questionnaire was used to collect the data presented in this report. The survey was administered using Microsoft Forms. All responses were anonymous and required a valid University of Twente account to participate.

Introduction Shown to Respondents

Dear survey participant,

As part of our ongoing efforts to improve the experience at the University of Twente, we are conducting a short survey about cafeteria food. Food plays an important role in our daily work life, whether it is grabbing a quick lunch, having coffee with colleagues, or finding healthy options during busy days. With this survey, we aim to understand your experiences and preferences regarding price, quality, variety, and availability of food and drinks on campus.

Your feedback will help us represent your interests more effectively in discussions with the university and service providers. The survey will only take a few minutes to complete, and your answers will remain anonymous.

— The PE-NUT team

Scope: This survey focuses on day-to-day cafeteria offerings for students and staff of the University of Twente. It excludes event catering and commercial alternatives on campus such as SPAR, Subway, Starbucks, Frosty's Poké Bowl, and food trucks.

Questionnaire

1. What is your role at the university? (Single choice)
 - Student
 - Promovendi (PhD or EngD)
 - Scientific Staff
 - Support Staff
 - Other
2. How often do you eat at a campus cafeteria? (Single choice)
 - Daily
 - Several times per week
 - Several times per month
 - Never

3. Do you have any specific dietary preferences or restrictions? (Multiple choice)
- None
 - Halal
 - Kosher
 - Gluten-free
 - Vegan
 - Vegetarian
 - Other
4. Do you feel that offered food items are sufficiently labeled so that you know whether they fit your dietary preferences or restrictions? (Single choice)
- Yes
 - No
5. Please rate the following statements. (Likert scale: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree)
[label*=5.]
- (a) The quality of food served by the cafeteria meets my expectations.
 - (b) I am satisfied with the taste of the food across different outlets.
 - (c) The prices of food at cafeterias are reasonable for the quality provided.
 - (d) The cafeterias provide good value for money compared to local alternatives (e.g., SPAR, Subway, Frosty's Poké Bowl).
 - (e) The pricing structure is clear and easy to understand.
 - (f) The daily menu provides enough variety to avoid repetition over time.
 - (g) The cafeteria menu accommodates my dietary needs and preferences.
 - (h) I feel I have a say or influence in the selection of menu items offered.
 - (i) I would like more opportunities to provide feedback on the menu options.
 - (j) I am satisfied with my overall experience of using the cafeterias.
 - (k) The cafeterias meet the needs of both students and staff equally well.
 - (l) I would like to have different cafeteria providers on campus.
6. Please rank the following factors in order of importance when deciding where to eat on campus (1 = most important, 6 = least important):
- Price

- Location
- Food Quality
- Food Variety
- Seating Area
- Speed of Service

7. If you could change one thing about the campus cafeteria (e.g., price, quality, menu variety), what would it be? (Short text)

- Open-ended response

8. Overall, how would you rate the cafeterias on campus? (1 = low, 10 = high)

9. How likely are you to recommend the cafeterias on campus to a friend or colleague? (0 = not at all likely, 10 = extremely likely)